

THE PLACE OF OXIDATIVE STRESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACUTE PURULENT OTITIS MEDIA

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At the present time, the rapid development of society and the economy takes place on the reactivity of the body. If the strength of the acting agent is very high, then arousal is provided in the body and which is replaced by maladaptation and subsequent death is ensured [10,11,12] If the strength of the acting agent is relatively low and prolonged, then arousal, adaptation and inhibition are provided in the body [11]. At the same time, a decrease in the general and specific resistance of the body is ensured. Accordingly, this kind of effect on the body is, a change in the temperature of the external environment, a temperature drop, improper bathing of children, living and eating conditions, various types of exposure that play a big role in the development of inflammatory processes at the level of the nasopharynx. With a decrease in the body's resistance, the inflammatory process has a chronic course and prevalence[5]. In such mandatory conditions, the pathological process of the middle ear develops [5,9]. Such a process necessarily develops against the background of oxidative stress and destructive changes in the body. At the same time, the indicators of the prooxidant, antioxidant system and endogenous intoxication in purulent otitis remain poorly understood and are an urgent problem.

The purpose of the study. To identify the state of prooxidant, antioxidant activity and indicators of endogenous intoxication in acute purulent otitis media. In connection with the task, the following were studied: the content of malondialdehyde (MDA)[6], catalase activity[3] and indicators of endogenous

intoxication MSM254 and MSM 280, as well as the coefficient of protein stability (CPS) [1].

The object of the study. The study was conducted in 20 patients with acute purulent otitis media of preschool age in the RNCEMPSF center in the city of Samarkand.

The data obtained and their discussion. When studying the activity of the prooxidant blood system in the blood of preschool children, that is, the amount of MDA was 3.76 ± 0.1 mmol/l, while the antioxidant activity of catalase was Catalase, 0.89 ± 0.01 mk-cat/s·l, the MDA/catalase coefficient was 4.2 ± 0.1 , the indicators of endogenous intoxication of MSM 254- 0.250 ± 0.003 in.units. MSM280- 0.280 ± 0.002 units. Where the CPS was 1.12 ± 0.01 .

In the study of patients admitted to the ENT department of the RNCEMPSF with acute purulent otitis media, an increase in the activity of the prooxidant system was revealed. At the same time, the MDA content increased compared to the norm to 9.0 ± 1.3 mmol/l ($p < 0.01$) Catalase, 0.25 ± 0.1 mk-cat/s·l, the MDA/catalase coefficient increased and amounted to 45.0 ± 7.5 ($P < 0.01$) Against the background of an increase in the activity of the prooxidant system, a decrease in the antioxidant system The patients' body revealed an increase in the indicators of endogenous intoxication of MSM 254 - up to 0.876 ± 0.03 units ($P < 0.001$), MSM280 up to 0.774 ± 0.02 units. ($P < 0.001$), a decrease in protein resistance to the CPS to 0.88 ± 0.01 ($P < 0.001$) compared with the usual indicator of the child's body.

If the data obtained is interpreted with the data of scientists. In preschool children with purulent otitis media, against the background of an increase in the activity of prooxidant activity and a decrease in antioxidant activity, an average degree of endogenous intoxication and a decrease in protein resistance against this kind of oxidative stress are observed [2,4, 7,8].

Based on the data obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Oxidative stress on the background of purulent otitis media in children up to school age contributes to the development of an average degree of endogenous intoxication and contributes to a decrease in protein stability and the development of destructive changes in the body.

Literature

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